

Assessing environmental and market implications of steel decarbonisation strategies in Brazil

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Executive Summary

This study examines the transition to low-carbon steel production in Brazil, highlighting its environmental and economic implications. The results show that adopting cleaner technologies can reduce emissions by 69% while also lowering steel prices by up to 38%, challenging the assumption that decarbonization comes at a financial cost. Brazil's abundant renewable energy resources and potential for green hydrogen production position the country as a key player in the global green steel economy. Furthermore, the study demonstrates that using the Input-Output Matrix and the Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO) model is an effective method for analyzing sectoral interactions and economic impacts.

To ensure a successful transition, policymakers should establish clear regulations for green hydrogen production, implement subsidies and tax incentives to support clean energy investments, and enhance grid expansion and storage capacity. Strengthening steel recycling systems and promoting electric arc furnace adoption will further reduce emissions and energy demand. Additionally, long-term policy stability, carbon pricing mechanisms, and international trade agreements will be essential to securing investment and ensuring competitiveness in global markets. A just transition must also be prioritized by investing in workforce training programs to prepare for shifts in employment within the steel sector.

1. Introduction

The steel industry is a significant contributor to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Brazil, accounting for approximately 4% of the country's total emissions and 30% of CO₂ emissions within the industrial sector (4th National Communication of Brazil to the UNFCCC). Steel production in Brazil relies on three main routes: BF-BOF using coal (69%), BF-BOF using charcoal (7%), and EAF (23%). These methods are both energy- and carbon-intensive, primarily due to the reliance on metallurgical coal as the main energy source.

Globally, the steel industry is exploring more sustainable production routes incorporating biomass, natural gas, and green hydrogen. Studies suggest that Brazil has strong potential to become a key player in green iron and steel production, positioning itself as a future exporter and contributor to sector-wide decarbonization (Agora Industry, Wuppertal Institute & Lund University, 2021; Wuppertal Institute, 2023; Ellersdorfer et al., 2024; Bilici et al., 2024).

However, as noted by the IPCC (2022), additional knowledge is required to fully understand the sectoral interactions involved in the transformation process. Input-output (I-O) analysis provides a powerful tool for addressing this complexity by extending traditional life cycle assessment (LCA) methodologies. This approach enables a comprehensive evaluation of economic and environmental impacts while allowing the introduction of new supply chains as emerging industrial activities.

This study aims to assess the environmental and market implications of steel decarbonization strategies in Brazil by analyzing both the current and projected carbon footprint of major steelmaking routes and their effect on steel prices. By applying modifications to a baseline I-O table, a new decarbonization scenario can be created, enabling a comparative analysis of economic and environmental impacts. This methodology will help answer key research questions:

- What are the impacts of transitioning to alternative technological routes for steel production in Brazil?
- To what extent can Brazil contribute to global decarbonization through green steel exports?

By addressing these questions, this research seeks to provide insights into how Brazil can position itself as a leader in sustainable steel production while mitigating industrial emissions and supporting the global energy transition.

2. Methodology

2.1. *The hybrid input-output model*

The model adopted in this study is structured as a SUT, of which a schematic representation is provided in figure 1. The software implementation was based on the open-source Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO) framework (Tahavori ET AL., 2021 and the model's underlying database is the hybrid-units version of Exiobase, with adaptations applied by Rinaldi et al. (2024). Those adaptations included the aggregation of electricity into 'Electricity from fossil fuels', 'from nuclear' and 'from

2.2. Decarbonization Scenario for Brazil

The scenarios are derived from Hebeda et al. (2023). The scenarios are modelled by changing the market share of each steel production route in Brazil. Baseline represents the current Brazilian steelmaking routes' market shares and Decarbonization represents 2050's market shares, as described in Figure 2. The Decarbonization scenario is alligned with IEA's (2020) global climate neutrality objective by 2050. Production levels were maintained constant in order to allow an analysis restricted to the impacts of technology variation.

Figure 2: Brazilian steelmaking routes' market shares in the baseline and decarbonization scenarios.

Source: Adapted from Hebeda et al. (2023).

The projected steel supply mixes would result in price variations due to the differing costs associated with each production technology. Beginning with the original Exiobase activity, technology-specific multipliers were applied to the 'Operating surplus: Consumption of fixed capital' factor within the value-added matrix (V) to represent varying expenditure requirements (Table 1). While other cost differences may exist, capital cost was assumed to be the primary distinguishing factor among the analysed technologies.

Table 1: Multipliers of capital expenditures assumed

Steelmaking routes	Multipliers
Steel production with charcoal inj to BF	1,004
Steel production with H2 inj to BF	0,15
Steel production BF-BOF + CCUS	1,25
Steel production with charcoal inj to BF + CCUS	1,254
Steel production through 100%H2-DR	0,125
Steel production through NG-DR	0,125

Source: Rinaldi et al. (2024)

3. Results

Results indicate that implementing new low-carbon technologies in Brazil's steel sector not only reduces emissions by 69% but also lowers steel prices by up to 38%, as shown in Figure 3. While the emissions reduction is expected, the price decrease may seem counterintuitive at first. However, this trend can be explained by a combination of factors.

Figure 3: Steel price and GHGs footprint comparison between baseline and decarbonisation scenarios.

The first factor is technological efficiency gains. New steel plants tend to adopt more efficient production methods, reducing energy and raw material costs per ton of steel. Additionally, advanced technologies such as hydrogen-based direct reduction and electric arc furnaces often have lower operational costs than traditional blast furnaces, especially when clean energy is abundant and affordable.

Another key factor is lower energy costs. Conventional steelmaking processes, such as coke-making, are highly energy-intensive. By minimizing or eliminating these steps, new technologies significantly reduce overall energy expenses, directly impacting the final cost of steel.

Finally, changes in input-output dynamics also play a major role. Input-output matrix analysis captures shifts in supply chain dependencies as new technologies are introduced. If steel plants rely on different inputs—such as less coal and more electricity or biomass—the cost structure of production changes. As demand shifts toward more cost-effective materials and energy sources, manufacturing costs decrease, ultimately driving steel prices down.

Beyond its direct impact on emissions and pricing, low-carbon steel also delivers broader environmental benefits across multiple industries. When used in construction, vehicle manufacturing, and other sectors, its reduced carbon footprint helps lower emissions throughout the entire supply chain, creating a continuous cycle of decarbonization across the economy.

Figure 4 illustrates the regional impact of emissions across different parts of the world. The bars represent the absolute difference in emissions between the two analyzed scenarios. Brazil emerges as the most affected region, as it is both the primary producer and consumer of low-carbon steel.

The orange segment highlights the short-term impact of constructing new steel plants, which initially leads to a peak in emissions due to infrastructure development. However, in the long run, as these plants enter operation and remain active until 2050, emissions decline significantly. Overall, Brazil achieves a total emissions reduction of 77 Mt, demonstrating the long-term environmental benefits of transitioning to low-carbon steel production.

Figure 4: Comparative emissions reduction by region from steel sector decarbonization in Brazil (2025-2050), focusing on the impacts on Brazil

Zooming in on other regions, Figure 5 highlights the variations in emissions across different parts of the world. These differences arise from each region's unique level of steel imports from Brazil, as well as the varying types and quantities of inputs they supply to Brazil's steel production. However, despite these regional disparities, all regions experience a net reduction in emissions over the long term.

Figure 5: Comparative emissions reduction by region from steel sector decarbonization in Brazil (2025-2050), focusing on the other regions besides Brazil

5. Discussion

The results highlight a crucial insight: decarbonizing Brazil's steel sector is not only an environmental necessity but also an economically viable transition. The simultaneous reduction in emissions and steel prices challenges the conventional notion that sustainability efforts come at a financial cost. Instead, the study suggests that cleaner production routes can enhance efficiency, lower operational expenses, and reshape supply chain dependencies in ways that benefit both producers and consumers.

A particularly important implication is Brazil's strategic position in the global green steel economy. With abundant renewable energy resources and the potential to scale up biomass and green hydrogen production, Brazil could emerge as a key player in supplying low-carbon steel to international markets. This transition aligns with the growing global demand for cleaner industrial materials and corporate sustainability commitments.

The results also emphasize the broader spillover effects of decarbonization. As cleaner steel enters supply chains in construction, automotive, and manufacturing, emissions reductions extend beyond the steel sector, amplifying sustainability gains across the economy. This reinforces the idea that industrial decarbonization can trigger a cascading effect, accelerating progress toward national and global climate goals.

To fully capitalize on the economic and environmental benefits of green steel, targeted policies and technological advancements are necessary. A strong regulatory framework for green hydrogen production in Brazil is essential, along with government programs that provide support through subsidies, tax credits, and investments in electrolyzer capacity. Strengthening renewable energy integration is also critical. Policies that promote grid expansion, energy storage, and long-term renewable power purchase agreements (PPAs) could help stabilize costs and ensure a reliable energy supply for low-carbon steel production.

In terms of steel production routes, it is important to highlight that in the decarbonization scenario, there is an increase in production through scrap-based electric arc furnaces (EAFs). Improving steel recycling rates is therefore essential to reducing emissions and energy demand. Incentivizing end-of-life steel recovery and investing in advanced sorting technologies would support this transition and further enhance sustainability.

While the findings offer valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. The study relies on certain technological, infrastructure, and market assumptions, including the expectation that new production routes will achieve projected efficiency gains and cost reductions. However, real-world implementation may face technical, financial, and logistical challenges that could alter these projections. The transition to low-carbon steel requires large-scale investments, and delays or cost overruns could impact its feasibility. Additionally, the success of green steel production depends on supportive policies, including carbon pricing, subsidies, and international trade agreements. Uncertainty in regulatory frameworks could influence investment decisions and slow down adoption.

To address these limitations and refine transition strategies, further research should conduct a more detailed examination of capital costs, operational expenses, and potential financing mechanisms for green steel production. Carbon tariffs and trade policies may significantly influence the competitiveness and global demand for green steel exports, making their inclusion in future analyses crucial for informing policy developments in Brazil and other countries. Another essential aspect of the energy transition is its social impact. Evaluating workforce training needs and job distribution shifts resulting from changes in the steel sector will be key to ensuring a just transition that supports economic development alongside decarbonization efforts.

7. Conclusion

The transition to low-carbon steel production offers significant opportunities but also presents challenges that require strategic coordination. While the findings highlight substantial environmental and economic benefits, achieving these outcomes will depend on collaborative efforts between industry leaders, policymakers, and researchers. Overcoming infrastructure limitations, expanding clean energy capacity, and implementing policies that align with global market trends will be essential for ensuring Brazil's competitive position in the green steel economy.

This study demonstrates that using the Input-Output Matrix and the Multifunctional Analysis of Regions through Input-Output (MARIO) model is an effective approach for analysing the complex interactions across economic sectors. These methods provide a comprehensive framework for assessing the broader implications of industrial transitions, capturing shifts in supply chains, and evaluating both direct and indirect economic and environmental impacts.

By leveraging its renewable energy potential and investing in sustainable technologies, Brazil has the opportunity to become a key global supplier of low-carbon steel. However, long-term success will require sustained commitment, financial support, and regulatory

certainty to drive innovation, attract investment, and facilitate a just transition for the workforce.

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